

Implementation of Neural Networks in Predicting the Understanding Level of Students Subject

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Abstract

This paper implements artificial neural network in predicting the understanding level of student's course. By implementing artificial neural network based on backpropagation algorithm, an institution can give a fair decision in prediction level of students' understanding of particular course / subject. This method was chosen because it is able to determine the level of students' understanding of the subject based on input from questionnaires given. The study was conducted into two ways, namely training and testing. Data will be divided into two parts, the first data for the training process and the second reading data of the testing process. The training process aims to identify or search for goals that are expected to use a lot of patterns. Thus, it will be able to produce the best pattern to train the data. After reaching the goal of training which is based on the best pattern, then it will be tested with new data to see the accuracy of the target data using Matlab 6.1 software. The results show that it can accelerate the process of prediction of students' understanding. By using architectural models 6-50-1 as the best model, some architectural models are tested and the result of prediction is reach to 87.75%. In other word, this model is good enough to make predictions on the level of students' understanding of the subject.

Keywords: Artificial neural network; Backpropogation; Level Comprehension; Student; Subject

1. Introduction

Private collegelike AMIK Tunas BangsaPematangsiantar, North Sumatera, Indonesia has not introduced a system of determining the level of students' understanding of the subject based on professional teaching activities. The process of learning is one of the activities in a college / institution in academic life [1]. The role is inseparable from professional teaching activities. In the learning process there needs to be a two-way relationship between students and professional teachers [2]. This meant that there was good cooperation during the learning process takes place. Evaluations are conducted by the university / institution of the learning process is necessary to end the semester. It is intended that no assessment of students and faculty professional. For these students aimed at assessing the level of understanding and absorption of the subjects that are taught and for faculty professional aims to assess the extent to which professional teaching activities can be channeled towards the subjects that diampunypengetahuanya for 1 (one) semester. Therefore, the university or higher institution can provide equitable policies.

Prediction of students' understanding of the subject by professional teaching staff can help the university or higher institution in making policies on the future of professional teaching activities [3,4]. To determine the level of students' understanding of the subject is

done by assessing (scoring) through questionnaires. Questionnaires were administered to represent the entire process of assessing the level of understanding of students on the course. Having obtained the target or goal of the assessment is desired then made the determination (determination) for the level of students' understanding of the subject by professional teachers. Artificial Neural Networks (ANN) is one of the information processing systems that are designed to mimic the way the human brain works in resolving a problem with the learning process through changes in weight [7-11]. There are many techniques that can be used for the implementation of Artificial Neural Networks one of them is Backpropagation [12-15]. Artificial Neural Networks by using the backpropagation algorithm has been widely used to solve some problems, one prediction problem.

This paper implements artificial neuralnetworkin predictingthe understanding level ofstudent'ssubject. This method was chosen because it is able to determine the level of students' understanding of the subject based on input from questionnaires given. The study was conducted into two ways, namely training and testing. Data will be divided into two parts, the first data for the training process and the second reading of the testing process. The training process aims to identify or search for goals that are expected to use a lot of patterns, then it will be able to produce the best pattern to train the data. After reaching the goal of training which is based on the best pattern, then it will be tested with new data to see at the accuracy of the target using Matlab 6.1 software.

The rest of this paper is organized as follow. Section 2 presents rudimentary of artificial intelegence, artificial neural networks and backpropagation algorithm. Section 3 presents experimental design. Section 4 presents results and following by discussion. Finally, the conclusion of this work is presented in Section 5.

2. Rudimentary

2.1. Artificial Intelegence

AI is a field of study based on the premise that intelligent thought can be regarded as a form of computation - one that can be formalized and ultimately mechanized. To achieve this, however, two major issues need to be addressed. The first issue is knowledge representation, and the second is knowledge manipulation [1]. The main aim of Artificial Intelligence (AI) is to study how to build artificial systems that perform tasks normally performed by human beings. This concept was introduced in 1956 in the Darthmouth conference. From that moment on a lot of effort has been made and many goals have been achieved but unfortunately many failures as well. Today, the AI is a very important discipline and it includes a number of well-recognized and mature areas including Expert Systems [16-18], Fuzzy Logic [19-22], Genetic Algorithms [23-25], Language Processing, Logic Programming, Planning and Scheduling, Neural Networks and Robotics [26]. The general problem of simulating intelligence has been simplified to specific sub-problems which have certain characteristics or capabilities that an intelligent system should exhibit. The following characteristics have received the most attention:

- a. Deduction, reasoning, problem solving (embodied agents, neural networks, statistical approaches to AI);
- b. Knowledge representation (ontologies);
- c. Planning (multi-agent planning and cooperation);
- d. Learning (machine learning);

- e. Natural Language Processing (information retrieval – text mining, machine translation);
- f. Motion and Manipulation (navigation, localization, mapping, motion planning);
- g. Perception (speech recognition, facial, recognition, object recognition);
- h. Social Intelligence (empathy simulation);
- i. Creativity (artificial intuition, artificial imagination); and
- j. General Intelligence (Strong AI).

Classical AI approaches focus on individual human behavior, knowledge representation and inference methods. Distributed Artificial Intelligence (DAI), on the other hand, focuses on social behavior, *i.e.*, cooperation, interaction and knowledge-sharing among different units (agents). The process of finding a solution in distributed resolution problems relies on sharing knowledge about the problem and cooperation among agents. It was from these concepts that the idea of intelligent multi-agent technology emerged. An agent is an autonomous cognitive entity which understands its environment, *i.e.*, it can work by itself and it has an internal decision-making system that acts globally around other agents. In multi-agent systems, a group of mobile autonomous agents cooperate in a coordinated and intelligent manner in order to solve a specific problem or classes of problems [27].

2.2. Artificial Neural Networks (NN)

Artificial Neural Network (ANN) is a computational model, which is based on Biological Neural Network. Artificial Neural Network is often called as Neural Network (NN) (See Figure 1). From Figure 1, to build artificial neural network, artificial neurons, also called as nodes, are interconnected [7,8]. The architecture of NN is very important for performing a particular computation. Some neurons are arranged to take inputs from outside environment. These neurons are not connected with each other, so the arrangement of these neurons is in a layer, called as Input layer. All the neurons of input layer are producing some output, which is the input to next layer. The architecture of NN can be of single layer or multilayer. In a single layer Neural Network, only one input layer and one output layer is there, while in multilayer neural network, there can be one or more hidden layer. An artificial neuron is an abstraction of biological neurons and the basic unit in an ANN [9,10]. The Artificial Neuron receives one or more inputs and sums them to produce an output. Usually the sums of each node are weighted, and the sum is passed through a function known as an activation or transfer function. The objective here is to develop a data classification algorithm that will be used as a general-purpose classifier. To classify any database first, it is required to train the model. The proposed training algorithm used here is a Hybrid BP-GA [11,12]. After successful training, user can give unlabeled data to be classified.

Figure 1. ANN Model

The synapses or connecting links: that provide weights, w_j , to the input values, x_j for $j = 1 \dots m$. An additional function that sums the weighted input values to compute the input to the activation function as follow:

$$V = W_0 + \sum_{j=1}^m W_j X_j \quad (1)$$

where, w_0 is called the bias, is a numerical value associated with the neuron. It is convenient to think of the bias as the weight for an input x_0 whose value is always equal to one, so that;

$$V = \sum_{j=1}^m W_j X_j \quad (2)$$

An activation function g: that maps v to $g(v)$ the output value of the neuron. This function is a monotone function. The logistic (also called the sigmoid) function $g(v) = \frac{e^v}{1+e^v}$ as the activation function works best. The practical value of the logistic function arises from the fact that it is almost linear in the range where g is between 0.1 and 0.9 but has a squashing effect on very small or very large values [28].

2.3. Architecture of Backpropagation

The back-propagation learning algorithm (BPLA) has become famous learning algorithms among ANNs. In the learning process, to reduce the inaccuracy of ANNs, BPLAs use the gradient-descent search method to adjust the connection weights. The structure of a back-propagation ANN is shown in Figure 2. The output of each neuron is the aggregation of the numbers of neurons of the previous level multiplied by its corresponding weights. The input values are converted into output signals with the calculations of activation functions. Backpropagation ANNs have been widely and successfully applied in diverse applications, such as pattern recognition, location selection and performance evaluations [29].

Figure 2. Back-propagation ANN

There are several algorithms that can be used to create an artificial neural network, but the Back propagation was chosen because it is probably the easiest to implement, while preserving efficiency of the network. Backward Propagation Artificial Neural Network (ANN) use more than one input layers (usually 3). Each of these layers must be either of the following:

- a. Input Layer – This layer holds the input for the network
- b. Output Layer – This layer holds the output data, usually an identifier for the input.
- c. Hidden Layer – This layer comes between the input layer and the output layer. They serve as a propagation point for sending data from the previous layer to the next layer [30].

2.4. Backpropagation Neural Network

Phases in Backpropagation Technique algorithm can be divided into two phases: propagation and weight update.

Phase 1: Propagation

Each propagation involves the following steps:

1. Forward propagation of a training pattern's input is given through the neural network in order to generate the propagation's output activations.
2. Back propagation of the output activations propagation through the neural network using the training pattern's target in order to generate the deltas of all output and hidden neurons.

Phase 2: Weight Update

For each weight-synapse:

1. Multiply its input activation and output delta to get the gradient of the weight.
2. Bring the weight in the direction of the gradient by adding a ratio of it from the weight.

This ratio impacts on the speed and quality of learning; it is called the learning rate. The sign of the gradient of a weight designates where the error is increasing; this is

why the weight must be updated in the opposite direction. The phases 1 and 2 are repeated until the performance of the network is satisfactory [31].

2.5. Evaluating the Performance of the Models

The main measures used for evaluating the performance of machine learning techniques for predicting the software effort are as follows [32]:

a. Sum Squared Error (SSE)

The sum squared error is defined as.

$$\sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - A_i)^2 \quad (3)$$

where

P_i = Estimated value for data point i ;

A_i = Actual value for the data point i ;

n = Total number of data points.

b. Mean Squared Error (MSE)

The mean squared error is defined as.

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - A_i)^2 \quad (4)$$

where

P_i = Estimated value for data point i ;

A_i = Actual value for the data point i ;

n = Total number of data points.

c. Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE)

The root mean squared error is defined as.

$$\sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (P_i - A_i)^2} \quad (5)$$

where

P_i = Estimated value for data point i ;

A_i = Actual value for the data point i ;

n = Total number of data points.

d. Mean Absolute Error (MAE)

The mean absolute error measures of how far the estimates are from actual values.

It could be applied to any two pairs of numbers, where one set is "actual" and the other is an estimate prediction.

$$\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |P_i - A_i| \quad (6)$$

where

P_i = Estimated value for data point i ;

A_i = Actual value for the data point i ;

n = Total number of data points.

3. Experiment Design

3.1. Data Collection

In this study, the pattern recognition system and prediction of students' understanding of the subject is presented. Data were obtained from questionnaires distributed to students grouped by subjects that taught by faculty as a lecturer. As for the format of a questionnaire given to students in the form of questions by 30 questions in which each question represents the study variables (See Figure 3). The research variables are learning, skills, assessment and workload, guidance and counseling, learning resources and standards and targets. Students need to give a score of 1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=moderate, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree, such as the following format:

Questionnaire Evaluation of Lectures by Students

Courses :
Semester :
Supporting lecturer :
Department / Study Program :
Put across (X) in the appropriate option,

1=Strongly Disagree, 2=Disagree, 3=Moderate, 4=Agree, 5=Strongly Agree						
No	Commentary	Score				
A	Learning	1	2	3	4	5
1.	At the beginning of the lecture the lecturer expressed about the ability of the students obtained after following this course					
2	At the beginning of the lecture the lecturer explained well about the main points of the lecture and learning methods					
3	At the beginning of the lecture the lecturer explained well about the system of assessment of students					
4	Textbooks, workbooks and / or handouts are provided with good					
5	Bibliography required to process a given learning courses delivered very clearly by lecturers					
6	Lecturers prepare teaching materials with good lectures					
7	Lecturers to inspire and motivate					
8	Lecturers explain and facilitate learning activities well					
9	Textbooks, workbooks and / or handouts to help me understand lectures					
10	I get a lot of knowledge of the way of learning this course					
11	I think working in a group is an effective way to learn					
12	Through this course I get a good understanding					
13	Lecturer always assigns the end of each subject					
14	Results correction tasks immediately returned by the lecturers					
B	Skills	1	2	3	4	5
15	I have learned to think critically as a result of the activity of this course					

16	I have learned to present ideas in a way that is clearly as a result of the activity of this course					
17	I have developed communication skills as a result of the activity of this course					
18	I have developed my ability to work in groups or teams as a result of the work I do in these lectures					
C	AssessmentAndWorkload	1	2	3	4	5
19	How to vote in this study clearly					
20	How to vote in this study clearly Assessment of this study into account the work of individuals and work groups					
D	GuidanceAndCounseling	1	2	3	4	5
21	I get enough of tutoring from the lecturer's					
22	There is a good academic guidance on the choice of subjects which correspond to the needs and interests of my					
E	Learning Resources	1	2	3	4	5
23	I easily get reading materials to complete this course					
24	The use of LCD projectors in learning easier for me to understand what is being taught					
25	Libraries University / Faculty / Department have enough books, journals and other reading materials for the completion of this course					
F	Standards AndTargets	1	2	3	4	5
26	I understand very well the terms desired of us in the process of learning this course					
27	I see clearly how the parts of this lecture strung together to accomplish the desired target					
28	I understand how the activity of our lectures rated					
G	Public Impact and Quality	1	2	3	4	5
29	Overall I am satisfied with the quality of learning from this course					
30	This subject has an impact on how I make decisions					

Figure 3. Student Questionnaire Data

The charging process is done by taking a sample of some of the classes are categorized by subjects that taught by professional teacher. The list of criteria to determine the prediction of students' understanding of the subject is given in Table 1 as follows:

Table 1. The List of Criteria

No	Criteria	Variable	Description	Weight
1	Learning	A	Strongly Agree	1
			Agree	0.8
			Moderate	0.6
			Disagree	0.4
			Strongly Disagree	0.2
2	Skills	B	Strongly Agree	1
			Agree	0.8
			Moderate	0.6
			Disagree	0.4
			Strongly Disagree	0.2
3	Assessment And Workload	C	Strongly Agree	1
			Agree	0.8
			Moderate	0.6
			Disagree	0.4
			Strongly Disagree	0.2
4	Guidance And Counseling	D	Strongly Agree	1
			Agree	0.8
			Moderate	0.6
			Disagree	0.4
			Strongly Disagree	0.2
5	Learning Resources	E	Strongly Agree	1
			Agree	0.8
			Moderate	0.6
			Disagree	0.4
			Strongly Disagree	0.2
6	Standards And Targets	F	Strongly Agree	1
			Agree	0.8
			Moderate	0.6
			Disagree	0.4
			Strongly Disagree	0.2

3.2. Data Processing

Data processing is done with the help of matlab 6.1 software application. The raw data from a sample of 80 students will be divided into two parts, namely the test data and data testing. The raw data will be transformed into a table predetermined criteria in Table 2. As for the sample of data that has been processed and ditranformasi are as follows.

Table 2. Samples of Data that has been Transformed

NO	NIM	Name	Variable Input						Target
			Learning	Skills	assessment and workload	Guidance and counseling	learning Source	Standard and targets	Predictions
			X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7
1	201201010030	Marisi Hutagaol	0.8	1	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	1
2	201201010033	Rati Febriansari Hasibuan	0.8	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.6	1
3	201201010042	Agustina	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	1
4	201201010053	Nani Indrayati	0.2	1	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.6	1
5	201201010061	Alhamidu Tarigan	0.8	0.8	1	0.6	0.8	0.6	0
6	201201010066	Eko Setiawan	0.6	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	1
7	201201010093	Niah Lukuita Tarigan	1	1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	1
8	201201010098	Tumbur Joanparlo Hutabarat	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0
9	201201030002	Demancen Simarmata	0.6	0.8	1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0
10	201201030007	Indra Pratama	0.8	1	1	0.6	0.8	0.8	1
11	201201030010	Muhammad Abdul Aziz Dalimunte	1	0.6	1	0.6	0.6	0.6	1
12	201201030011	M. Rifai	0.8	1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.8	1
13	201201030013	Martono	0.6	0.8	0.8	0.6	0.2	0.8	0
14	201201030048	Ilka Yani	0.8	1	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.6	0
15	201201030052	Mila Sugiani	0.8	1	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.8	1
16	201201030055	Rudy Handa Syahputra	1	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	0
17	201201030059	Sri Fatmawati	0.6	1	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.6	1
18	201201030064	Effendi	0.8	1	0.6	0.6	0.8	0.8	1
19	201201030074	Muhammad Sofyan	1	0.8	1	0.6	0.2	0.6	0
20	201201030077	Rizal Apriadi	0.8	1	0.8	0.6	0.8	0.8	1
21	201201030083	Egi Yulianti Damanik	0.8	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.2	0.6	1
22	201201030091	Nela Puspa Sari	0.6	0.6	1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0
23	201201030102	Ahmad Latip	0.8	1	0.8	0.6	0.2	0.6	0
24	201201030104	Eko Susilo	1	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6	0
25	201201030106	Irwanto	0.6	1	1	0.6	0.8	0.6	1

Once the raw data is transformed into a table predetermined criteria, the next step is to determine the best architecture with patterns by performing a series of tests. The second stage is to predict the best architectural patterns obtained in the first stage. Testing process is carried out by entering the data and comparing the minimum error value is obtained from the best architectural pattern carried on the first stage.

3.3. Manual Design of Architectural Patterns

The desired outcome at this stage is the detection of a pattern determining best value for the level of students' understanding of the subject. The results are as follows:

- a. To determine the level of students' understanding of the course is based on professional teaching activities. Output from pemahan level there are 2 possibilities, namely "Understand" with weight 1 and "Not familiar" with weights0.
- b. Categorization "understand" or "do notunderstand"
 Category for "understand" is determined by the minimum error rate of the target "understand" that is 1. Those categorizations can be seen in Table 3 as follow:

Table 3. Data Categorization "understand"

No	Description	Error Minimum
1	VeryUnderstand	0.0000 - 0.0010
2	Understand	0.0011 - 0.0100
3	UnderstandEnough	0.0101 - 0.1000

Categorization "not understand" is determined by the minimum error level of 0. The targets "do not understand" that "do not understand" the categorization can be seen in Table 4 as follow:

Table 4. Data Categorization “notunderstand”

No	Description	Error Minimum
1	VeryNot Understand	0.0000 - 0.0010
2	Do Not Understand	0.0011 - 0.0100
3	Enough Not Understand	0.0101 - 0.1000

4. Results and Discussion

4.1. The Best Pattern Determination

Training and testing is done several times with different parameters to get the best results with the software application Matlab 6.1 Neural Network method in determining the best pattern for the level of students' understanding of subjects by professional teaching staff has three part process, namely:

- The process of data input and the target includes inputting learning, skills assessment and workload, guidance and counseling, learning resources and standards and targets. As the target is the level of students' understanding of the course
- The process of determining the results of processed data that includes data conversion process into a pre-determined weight, calculate the weight value into the back propagation stage.
- The results of the process of determining the data that is processed with Matlab 6.1 software application will be used to predict the level of student understanding terhadap subjects by comparing the value of the minimum error.

From the series of experiments performed using Matlab 6.1 software application with 6-50-1, 6-75-1, 6-100-1, 6-50-75-1 and architectural patterns obtained 6-75-100-1. The best at 6-50-1 models with attribute parameters as follows:

ActivationfunctiontoHiddenLayer : Tansig
 ActivationfunctiontoOutputLayer : Logsig
 TypeTraining : Traingd
 HiddenNeuronLayernumber : 50
 Learningrate : 0.1
 ErrorlimitsMaximum : 0,001
 Showlimit : 1000
 EpochlimitMaximum : 5000000
 Momentum : 0.8

Of the parameters used to model architectural epochs 6-50-1 with 166828 and MSE0.0009991940 shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Architecture 6-50-1 Achieve Goal

Of the five models tested architecture, architectural models 6-50-1 obtained with the smallest MSE. 6-50-1MSE results are given in Table 5 below:

Table 5. Results MSE6-50-1 Architecture Model using Matlab 6.1 Application

No	Target	Output	Error	SSE
1	1	0.9792	0.0208	0.0004326400
2	1	0.9443	0.0557	0.0031024900
3	1	0.9565	0.0435	0.0018922500
4	1	0.9944	0.0056	0.0000313600
5	0	0.0409	-0.0409	0.0016728100
6	1	0.9891	0.0109	0.0001188100
7	1	0.9858	0.0142	0.0002016400
8	0	0.0376	-0.0376	0.0014137600
9	0	0.0181	-0.0181	0.0003276100
10	1	0.9861	0.0139	0.0001932100
11	1	0.9701	0.0299	0.0008940100
12	1	0.9985	0.0015	0.0000022500
13	0	0.0206	-0.0206	0.0004243600
14	0	0.0509	-0.0509	0.0025908100
15	1	0.9755	0.0245	0.0006002500
16	0	0.0576	-0.0576	0.0033177600
17	1	0.9540	0.0460	0.0021160000
18	1	0.9792	0.0208	0.0004326400
19	0	0.0131	-0.0131	0.0001716100
20	1	0.9931	0.0069	0.0000476100
			Total	0.0199838800
			MSE	0.0009991940

To see the results of the comparison data MSE all architectural models are tested using matlab 6.1 application is complete, it can be seen from Table 6 as follow:

Table 6. Comparison of each Model Epoch and every MSE Architecture Model

	6-50-1	6-75-1	6-100-1	6-50-75-1	6-75-100-1
Epochs	166828	>2000000	38820	25145	19255
MSE	0.0009991940	Not Defined	0.0009995025	0.0009997820	0.0009993985

4.2. Students Understanding Level Predictions of the Course

The last stage is the prediction of student understanding of the subjects that diabawakan by professional teachers. This stage is done by comparing the minimum error value of the results obtained. With 6-50-1 architecture model, the data will be predicted to see how accurate the model is able to recognize data. The desired results of this final stage are to get the minimum error value for the prediction of architectural patterns. The results are as follows:

- a. Categorization “understand and do not understand”
 Categorization “understand” is determined by the minimum error rate, where “familiar” with a weight of 1 and “not familiar” with weights 0
- b. Categorization minimum error for prediction data to understand and do not understand can be seen in Table 7 as follow:

Table 7. Data Categorization Prediction

No	Description	<i>Error Minimum</i>
1	Understand	0.0000 – 0.0010
2	Do Not Understand	0.0011 – 0.0100

Data to be predicted to see correctness level can be seen in Table 8 as follow.

Table 8. Results Prediction Model 6-50-1

Prediction 6-50-1		Prediction		Information
No	NIM	Real Data	JST	Result
1	201201030083	1	0,00092	True
2	201201030091	0	0,00033	True
3	201201030102	0	0,00036	True
4	201201030104	1	0,00078	True
5	201201030106	1	0,00082	True
6	201201030111	1	0,00038	True
7	201201030127	1	0,00038	True
8	201201030142	0	0,0036	True
9	201201030148	1	0,00032	True
10	201201030156	0	0,0057	True
11	201201030157	0	0,0094	True
12	201201030159	1	0,0374	True
13	201201030160	0	0,008	True
14	201201030162	0	0,008	True
15	201201030173	0	0,0038	True
16	201201030175	0	0,0038	True

17	201201030209	0	0,8956	False
18	201301030001	0	0,0079	True
19	201301030002	0	0,0392	False
20	201301030003	0	0,0046	True
21	201301030007	0	0,0057	True
22	201301030012	0	0,0087	True
23	201301030018	0	0,0046	True
24	201301030024	0	0,008	True
25	201301030025	0	0,008	True
26	201301030030	0	0,006	True
27	201301030041	0	0,0081	True
28	201301030067	1	0,00058	True
29	201301030069	1	0,000374	True
30	201301030073	1	0,000375	True
31	201301030074	1	0,000375	True
32	201301030075	1	0,000363	True
33	201301030082	1	0,000374	True
34	201301030083	1	0,000375	True
35	201301030091	1	0,0373	True
36	201301030093	1	0,00056	True
37	201301030094	1	0,00059	True
38	201301030110	1	0,00059	True
39	201301030120	1	0,000373	True
40	201301030123	1	0,00056	True
41	201301030130	1	0,00032	True
42	201301030131	1	0,00056	True
43	201301030150	1	0,0373	True
44	201301030152	1	0,00056	True
45	201301030154	1	0,0387	True

By using architectural models 6-50-1 prediction results obtained 87.75%. In other words, this model is good enough to predict the level of students' understanding of the subject.

5. Conclusion

In this paper, implementation of artificial neural network in predicting the understanding level of student's subject has been presented. Based on the results and analysis of the previous chapter, the author can draw conclusions as follows:

- a. Adding lots of hidden layer during the training and testing, not a maximum results. To 5 models designed architecture, 6-50-75-1 is a model that has the largest MSE is 0.028540763
- b. Having carried out experiments in the training process and system testing is done using Matlab 6.1 software application. Neural Network Model used was 6-50-1, 6-75-1 models, the model 6-100-1, 6-50-75-1 models and models 6-75-100-1, can be obtained good results with a view MSE the smallest and fastest epochs is 6-50-1.
- c. With 6-50-1 architectural models, can make predictions on the students' understanding of the subject by showing the performance above 92%.

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